

PYTHON APPROACH: A FUZZY TIME SERIES FORECASTING TECHNIQUE IS USED TO PREDICT ONLINE RETAIL FOR FUEL BOOKING SERVICES

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Abstract:

This paper describes the implementation of the Fuzzy Time Series approach, which was produced by estimating the interval length using the distribution method. The duration of the interval is critical in the fuzzy forecasting approach since it affects the accuracy of the predicting findings. The goal of developing this forecasting model is to achieve higher predicting accuracy. In this analysis, Statistical data on fuel bookings in online shopping were utilized to test the methodology on a certain day. The Python programming language is utilized during data processing. Based on the FTS method's accuracy test, it is possible to conclude that this technique gives better forecasting outcomes.

Key Words: Fuzzy Time Series, Online Retail, Python.

Introduction:

To strengthen its market position in a competitive context and ensure long-term development, any organization must always seek ways to improve its efficiency. Different forecasting approaches and models are used to guide decision-making processes in various sectors of the economy in the face of uncertainty. However, the external environment's uncertainty and variability necessitate the use of scientifically sound management decision-making approaches at all stages of production process management, which necessitates quality planning and forecasting of the most important production indicators, as well as systematic adjustment of current and future plans. As we all know, a forecast is any statement about the future, and economic forecasting is a vast field. Makridakis et al. [1] define time series forecasting as a forecasting procedure using historical data observations. There are two types of time series forecasting methods: statistical and mathematical model-based forecasting and artificial intelligence-based forecasting [2]. Song and Chissom first suggested the notion of fuzzy time series (FTS) forecasting in 1993 [3]. The goal of developing fuzzy forecasting models is to achieve a high level of predicting accuracy by improving the three key stages: fuzzification, defuzzification, and fuzzy inference. A refined method of forecasting based on high-order intuitionistic fuzzy time series by transformed a historical fuzzy time series data into intuitionistic fuzzy time series data via defining their appropriate membership and non-membership function [4-7]. PyFTS is an open and free library coded in Python programming language that was developed by the MINDS Lab (Laboratory of Machine Intelligence and Data Science) and, also provides a set of transformation functions for pre-processing time series and a set of metrics and databases for benchmarking, in addition to implementing several FTS models [8-11].

Methodology:

Let E be the universe of discourse, where $E = \{d_i\}_{i=1}^n$. A fuzzy set A_i in the universe of discourse E is defined as follows:

$A_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{f_{A_i}(d_i)}{d_i}$, Where f_{A_i} is the membership function of the fuzzy set A_i , $f_{A_i}: E \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f_{A_i}(d_j)$ is the degree of membership of d_j in the fuzzy set A_i , $f_{A_i}(d_j) \in [0, 1]$ and $1 \leq j \leq n$.

Let $Y(t)$ ($t = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) be the universe of discourse in which fuzzy sets $f_i(t)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots$) are defined in the universe of discourse $Y(t)$. Assume that $F(t)$ is a collection of $f_i(t)$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots$), then $F(t)$ is called a fuzzy time series of $Y(t)$ ($t = 0, 1, 2, \dots$).

Assume that there is a fuzzy relationship $R(t-1, t)$, such that $F(t) = F(t-1) \circ R(t-1, t)$, where the symbol "o" represents the max-min composition operator, then $F(t)$ is called caused by $F(t-1)$.

Let $F(t-1) = A_i$ and let $F(t) = A_j$, where A_i and A_j are fuzzy sets, then the fuzzy logical relationship (FLR) between $F(t-1)$ and $F(t)$ can be denoted by $A_i \rightarrow A_j$, where A_i and A_j are called the left-hand side (LHS) and the right hand side (RHS) of the fuzzy logical relationship, respectively.

Fuzzy logical relationships having the same left-hand side can be grouped into a fuzzy logical relationship group (FLRG). For example, assume that the following fuzzy logical relationships exist:

$$A_i \rightarrow A_{ja}, A_i \rightarrow A_{jb}, A_i \rightarrow A_{jc}, \dots, A_i \rightarrow A_{jm}$$

Then these fuzzy logical relationships can be grouped into a fuzzy logical relationship group, shown as follows:

$$A_i \rightarrow A_{ja}, A_{jb}, A_{jc}, \dots, A_{jm}.$$

Let $F(t)$ be a fuzzy time series. If $F(t)$ is caused by $F(t-1), F(t-1), \dots$, and $F(t-n)$ then the fuzzy logical relationship between them can be represented by the “nth-order fuzzy logical relationship”, shown as follows:

$$F(t-n), \dots, F(t-2), F(t-1) \rightarrow F(t).$$

If $F(t-n) = A_{in}, \dots, F(t-2) = A_{i2}, F(t-1) = A_{i1}$ and $F(t) = A_j$, where $A_{in}, \dots, A_{i2}, A_{i1}$ and A_j are fuzzy sets, then the nth-order fuzzy logical relationship can be represented by $A_{in}, \dots, A_{i2}, A_{i1} \rightarrow A_j$, Where $A_{in}, \dots, A_{i2}$ and A_{i1} are called the antecedent fuzzy sets of the nth-order fuzzy logical relationship; $A_{in}, \dots, A_{i2}, A_{i1}$ and A_j are called the left hand-side and the right-hand side of the nth-order fuzzy logical relationship, respectively.

If there is the nth-order fuzzy logical relationships having the same left-hand side, shown as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{in}, \dots, A_{i2}, A_{i1} &\rightarrow A_{ja}, \\ A_{in}, \dots, A_{i2}, A_{i1} &\rightarrow A_{jb}, \\ A_{in}, \dots, A_{i2}, A_{i1} &\rightarrow A_{jc}, \\ &\dots \\ A_{in}, \dots, A_{i2}, A_{i1} &\rightarrow A_{jm}, \end{aligned}$$

Then these nth-order fuzzy logical relationships form a nth-order fuzzy logical relationships group, shown as follows: $A_{in}, \dots, A_{i2}, A_{i1} \rightarrow A_{ja}, A_{jb}, A_{jc}, \dots, A_{jm}$.

A Forecasting Method Based On High-Order Fuzzy Logical Relationships:

In this section, a proposed method based on high-order fuzzy logical relationships is now presented as follows:

Step 1:

Define the universe of discourse E , $E = [A - B, C + D]$ into intervals of equal length, where A and C are the minimum value and the maximum value of the historical data, respectively, and B and D are two proper positive real values to divide the universe of discourse E into n intervals $d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n$ of equal length.

Step 2:

Define the linguistic terms A_i represented by fuzzy sets, shown as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \frac{1}{d_1} + \frac{0.5}{d_2} + \frac{0}{d_3} + \frac{0}{d_4} + \dots + \frac{0}{d_{n-2}} + \frac{0}{d_{n-1}} + \frac{0}{d_n}, \\ A_2 &= \frac{0.5}{d_1} + \frac{1}{d_2} + \frac{0.5}{d_3} + \frac{0}{d_4} + \dots + \frac{0}{d_{n-2}} + \frac{0}{d_{n-1}} + \frac{0}{d_n}, \\ A_3 &= \frac{0}{d_1} + \frac{0.5}{d_2} + \frac{1}{d_3} + \frac{0.5}{d_4} + \dots + \frac{0}{d_{n-2}} + \frac{0}{d_{n-1}} + \frac{0}{d_n}, \\ A_{n-1} &= \frac{0}{d_1} + \frac{0}{d_2} + \frac{0}{d_3} + \frac{0}{d_4} + \dots + \frac{0.5}{d_{n-2}} + \frac{1}{d_{n-1}} + \frac{0.5}{d_n}, \\ A_n &= \frac{0}{d_1} + \frac{0}{d_2} + \frac{0}{d_3} + \frac{0}{d_4} + \dots + \frac{0}{d_{n-2}} + \frac{0.5}{d_{n-1}} + \frac{1}{d_n}, \end{aligned}$$

Where $A_1, A_2, \dots$ and A_n are linguistic terms represented by fuzzy sets.

Step 3:

Fuzzily each historical datum into a fuzzy set defined in step 2. If the historical datum belongs to d_i and the maximum membership value of A_i occurs at d_i , then the historical datum is fuzzified into A_i , where $1 \leq i \leq n$.

Step 4:

Construct the nth-order fuzzy logical relationships from the fuzzified historical datum of the training data set.

Step 5:

Transform each nth-order fuzzy logical relationship $A_{X_1}, A_{X_2}, A_{X_3}, \dots, A_{X_j}, \dots, A_{X_n} \rightarrow A_{X_r}$ into the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{X_1}, A_{X_{1+V(X_1)}}, A_{X_{1+V(X_1)+V(X_2)}}, \dots, A_{X_{1+V(X_1)+V(X_2)+\dots+V(X_i)+\dots+V(X_m)+V(X_n)}} \\ \dots \\ \rightarrow A_{X_{1+V(X_1)+V(X_2)+\dots+V(X_i)+\dots+V(X_m)+V(X_n)}} \end{aligned}$$

where $V(X_1), V(X_2), \dots$, and $V(X_n)$ are integers.

Step 6:

Let the transformed nth-order fuzzy logical relationships obtained in step 5 having the same left-hand side form a nth-order fuzzy logical relationship group. For example, let us consider the following transformed third-order fuzzy logical relationships:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{a_1}, A_{a_{1+V(a_1)}}, A_{a_{1+V(a_1)+V(a_2)}} &\rightarrow A_{a_{1+V(a_1)+V(a_2)+V(a_3)}}, \\ A_{b_1}, A_{b_{1+V(b_1)}}, A_{b_{1+V(b_1)+V(b_2)}} &\rightarrow A_{b_{1+V(b_1)+V(b_2)+V(b_3)}}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\dots$$

$$A_{k_1}, A_{k_1+V(k_1)}, A_{k_1+V(k_1)+V(k_2)} \rightarrow A_{k_1+V(k_1)+V(k_2)+V(k_3)}$$

Where $V(a_1) = V(b_1) = \dots = V(k_1)$ and $V(a_2) = V(b_2) = \dots = V(k_2)$, then these third-order fuzzy logical relationships can be grouped into a transformed third-order fuzzy logical relationships group, shown as follows:

$$A_X, A_{X+V(Y_1)}, A_{X+V(Y_1)+V(Y_2)} \rightarrow A_{X+V(Y_1)+V(Y_2)+V(a_3)}, A_{X+V(Y_1)+V(Y_2)+V(b_3)}, \dots, A_{X+V(Y_1)+V(Y_2)+V(k_3)}$$

where $X = a_1, b_1, \dots, k_1$, $V(Y_1) = V(a_1) = V(b_1) = \dots = V(k_1)$ and $V(Y_2) = V(a_2) = V(b_2) = \dots = V(k_2)$.

Step 7:

Choose a transformed nth-order fuzzy logical relationship group for prediction. Assume that $F(t - n) = A_{in}$, $F(t - (n - 1)) = A_{i(n-1)}, \dots, F(t - 2) = A_{i2}$, and $F(t - 1) = A_{i1}$, and assume that we want to predict $F(t)$, where $A_{i1}, A_{i2}, \dots$, and A_{in} are fuzzy sets. Based on the transformed nth-order fuzzy logical relationship groups obtained in step 6, choose the corresponding transformed nth-order fuzzy logical relationship group for prediction. If the chosen transformed nth-order fuzzy logical relationship group is:

$$A_X, A_{X+V(Y_1)}, \dots, A_{X+V(Y_1)+V(Y_2)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})} \rightarrow A_{X+V(Y_1)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})+V(a_n)}, A_{X+V(Y_1)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})+V(b_n)}, \dots, A_{X+V(Y_1)+V(Y_2)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})+V(k_n)}$$

Where $A_{in} = A_X, A_{i(n-1)} = A_{X+V(Y_1)}, \dots, A_{i1} = A_{X+V(Y_1)+V(Y_2)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})}$

then replace X by the subscript in of the fuzzy set A_{in} to get the derived fuzzy sets $A_{in+V(Y_1)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})+V(a_n)}$, $A_{in+V(Y_1)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})+V(b_n)}$, and $A_{in+V(Y_1)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})+V(k_n)}$ for prediction.

Let $A_{j1} = A_{in+V(Y_1)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})+V(a_n)}$, let $A_{j2} = A_{in+V(Y_1)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})+V(b_n)}$, and let $A_{jk} = A_{in+V(Y_1)+\dots+V(Y_{n-1})+V(k_n)}$. Then, the forecasted variable $FVar$ is calculated as follows:

$$FVar = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k m_{ji}}{k} - m_{i1} \tag{1}$$

Where the maximum membership values of $A_{i1}, A_{j1}, A_{j2}, \dots$, and A_{jk} occur at the intervals $d_{i1}, d_{j1}, d_{j2}, \dots$, and d_{jk} , respectively, and $m_{i1}, m_{j1}, m_{j2}, \dots$, and m_{jk} are the midpoints of the intervals $d_{i1}, d_{j1}, d_{j2}, \dots$, and d_{jk} , respectively. The forecasted value FV is calculated as follows:

$$FV = RV(t - 1) + FVar \tag{2}$$

Where $RV(t - 1)$ is the real value on trading day t-1.

Research Design:

This analysis uses Statistical data on fuel bookings in online shopping, which will be used to calculate forecasting accuracy. Python is used to process data describes the study's flow.

Result and Discussion:

In this study, statistical data on fuel bookings in online shopping, the data are presented in Table.

	Invoice	StockCode	Description	Quantity	InvoiceDate	Price	Customer ID	Country
0	489434	85048	15CM CHRISTMAS GLASS BALL 20 LIGHTS	12	2009-12-01 07:45:00	6.95	13085.0	United Kingdom
1	489434	79323P	PINK CHERRY LIGHTS	12	2009-12-01 07:45:00	6.75	13085.0	United Kingdom
2	489434	79323W	WHITE CHERRY LIGHTS	12	2009-12-01 07:45:00	6.75	13085.0	United Kingdom
3	489434	22041	RECORD FRAME 7" SINGLE SIZE	48	2009-12-01 07:45:00	2.10	13085.0	United Kingdom
4	489434	21232	STRAWBERRY CERAMIC TRINKET BOX	24	2009-12-01 07:45:00	1.25	13085.0	United Kingdom

Figure 1: Using Python to process data describes the study's flow

index	InvoiceDate	Quantity ▲
0	2009-12-01 07:45:00	12.0
1	2009-12-01 07:45:00	12.0
2	2009-12-01 07:45:00	12.0
4	2009-12-01 07:45:00	24.0
3	2009-12-01 07:45:00	48.0

Figure 2: Statistical data of Invoice Date and Quantity on fuel bookings in online shopping

Figure 3: Statistical data of Index and Quantity on fuel bookings in online shopping

Trend Weighted FTS:

A0 ->

A0(0.0),A0(0.0),A0(0.0),A0(0.0),A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.002),A0(0.002),A0(0.002),A0(0.002),A0(0.002),A0(0.002),A0(0.002),A0(0.002),A0(0.002),A0(0.003),A0(0.003),A0(0.003),A0(0.003),A0(0.003),A0(0.003),A1(0.003),A10(0.003),A10(0.003),A10(0.003),A10(0.003),A10(0.004),A10(0.004),A10(0.004),A10(0.004),A10(0.004),A11(0.004),A11(0.004),A11(0.004),A12(0.004),A12(0.005),A12(0.005),A13(0.005),A13(0.005),A13(0.005),A13(0.005),A13(0.005),A13(0.005),A14(0.005),A14(0.005),A14(0.006),A14(0.006),A15(0.006),A15(0.006),A15(0.006),A15(0.006),A15(0.006),A17(0.006),A2(0.006),A2(0.006),A2(0.007),A2(0.007),A2(0.007),A24(0.007),A3(0.007),A3(0.007),A3(0.007),A3(0.007),A3(0.007),A3(0.008),A3(0.008),A3(0.008),A4(0.008),A4(0.008),A4(0.008),A4(0.008),A4(0.008),A4(0.008),A4(0.008),A4(0.009),A4(0.009),A4(0.009),A4(0.009),A5(0.009),A5(0.009),A5(0.009),A5(0.009),A5(0.009),A5(0.01),A5(0.01),A5(0.01),A6(0.01),A6(0.01),A6(0.01),A6(0.01),A6(0.01),A6(0.011),A6(0.011),A6(0.011),A6(0.011),A6(0.011),A6(0.011),A6(0.011),A7(0.011),A7(0.011),A7(0.012),A7(0.012),A7(0.012),A7(0.012),A7(0.012),A8(0.012),A8(0.012),A8(0.012),A8(0.012),A8(0.012),A8(0.013),A8(0.013),A8(0.013),A8(0.013),A8(0.013),A8(0.013),A8(0.013),A8(0.013),A8(0.013),A8(0.014),A8(0.014),A8(0.014),A8(0.014),A9(0.014),A9(0.014),A9(0.014),A9(0.014),A9(0.014),A9(0.014),A9(0.014),A9(0.014),A9(0.015),A9(0.015)

A3 ->

A0(0.018),A0(0.036),A0(0.055),A10(0.073),A10(0.091),A11(0.109),A11(0.127),A7(0.145),A7(0.164),A9(0.182)

A1 -> A7(1.0)

A7 ->

A0(0.002),A0(0.003),A0(0.005),A0(0.006),A0(0.008),A0(0.01),A0(0.011),A0(0.013),A0(0.014),A10(0.016),A10(0.017),A12(0.019),A12(0.021),A12(0.022),A13(0.024),A14(0.025),A16(0.027),A16(0.029),A17(0.03),A17(0.032),A21(0.033),A5(0.035),A6(0.037),A7(0.038),A7(0.04),A8(0.041),A8(0.043),A8(0.044),A8(0.046),A8(0.048),A9(0.049),A9(0.051),A9(0.052),A9(0.054),A9(0.056)

A5 ->

A0(0.013),A0(0.026),A0(0.038),A0(0.051),A0(0.064),A12(0.077),A12(0.09),A19(0.103),A19(0.115),A29(0.128),A6(0.141),A9(0.154)

A2 -> A10(0.048),A10(0.095),A11(0.143),A12(0.19),A4(0.238),A7(0.286)

A4 ->

A0(0.01),A10(0.019),A10(0.029),A10(0.038),A10(0.048),A10(0.057),A11(0.067),A12(0.076),A12(0.086),A16(0.095),A7(0.105),A7(0.114),A8(0.124),A9(0.133)

A13 ->

A0(0.001),A0(0.002),A0(0.003),A0(0.004),A0(0.005),A0(0.006),A0(0.007),A0(0.008),A0(0.009),A0(0.01),A0(0.011),A0(0.012),A10(0.013),A10(0.014),A11(0.015),A11(0.016),A12(0.017),A12(0.018),A13(0.019),A13(0.02),A13(0.021),A13(0.022),A14(0.023),A14(0.024),A14(0.025),A15(0.026),A15(0.027),A15(0.028),A15(0.029),A17(0.03),A17(0.031),A17(0.032),A19(0.033),A22(0.034),A24(0.035),A27(0.036),A28(0.037),A5(0.038),A6(0.039),A8(0.04),A8(0.041),A9(0.042),A9(0.043),A9(0.044)

A11 ->

A0(0.001),A0(0.002),A0(0.003),A0(0.005),A0(0.006),A10(0.007),A10(0.008),A11(0.009),A11(0.01),A11(0.012),A11(0.013),A12(0.014),A12(0.015),A12(0.016),A12(0.017),A12(0.019),A13(0.02),A13(0.021),A14(0.022),A14(0.023),A16(0.024),A16(0.026),A16(0.027),A16(0.028),A18(0.029),A19(0.03),A2(0.031),A21(0.033),A21(0.034),A22(0.035),A23(0.036),A6(0.037),A7(0.038),A7(0.039),A7(0.041),A8(0.042),A8(0.043),A8(0.044),A9(0.045),A9(0.046),A9(0.048)

A12 ->

A0(0.002),A0(0.003),A0(0.005),A0(0.006),A10(0.008),A10(0.01),A10(0.011),A10(0.013),A10(0.014),A10(0.016),A10(0.017),A10(0.019),A10(0.021),A11(0.022),A11(0.024),A12(0.025),A13(0.027),A13(0.029),A13(0.03),A15(0.032),A15(0.033),A18(0.035),A18(0.037),A20(0.038),A21(0.04),A29(0.041),A30(0.043),A6(0.044),A7(0.046),A7(0.048),A7(0.049),A8(0.051),A8(0.052),A8(0.054),A9(0.056)

A15 ->

A0(0.004),A0(0.007),A0(0.011),A0(0.014),A0(0.018),A10(0.022),A10(0.025),A12(0.029),A12(0.033),A13(0.036),A13(0.04),A14(0.043),A14(0.047),A17(0.051),A18(0.054),A20(0.058),A23(0.062),A24(0.065),A34(0.069),A4(0.072),A5(0.076),A8(0.08),A8(0.083)

A17 ->

A0(0.005),A0(0.011),A0(0.016),A0(0.021),A0(0.026),A10(0.032),A11(0.037),A12(0.042),A13(0.047),A13(0.053),A14(0.058),A15(0.063),A16(0.068),A16(0.074),A19(0.079),A19(0.084),A23(0.089),A25(0.095),A9(0.1)

A16 ->

A0(0.003),A0(0.006),A0(0.009),A0(0.012),A0(0.015),A10(0.018),A10(0.022),A12(0.025),A12(0.028),A14(0.031),A14(0.034),A15(0.037),A16(0.04),A18(0.043),A18(0.046),A20(0.049),A20(0.052),A22(0.055),A23(0.058),A24(0.062),A6(0.065),A6(0.068),A7(0.071),A9(0.074),A9(0.077)

A8 ->

A0(0.001),A0(0.002),A0(0.003),A0(0.004),A0(0.004),A0(0.005),A0(0.006),A0(0.007),A0(0.008),A0(0.009),A0(0.01),A10(0.011),A10(0.012),A11(0.012),A11(0.013),A11(0.014),A11(0.015),A11(0.016),A11(0.017),A11(0.018),A11(0.019),A11(0.02),A11(0.02),A12(0.021),A12(0.022),A13(0.023),A13(0.024),A13(0.025),A17(0.026),A19(0.027),A19(0.027),A21(0.028),A25(0.029),A3(0.03),A45(0.031),A5(0.032),A53(0.033),A6(0.034),A7(0.035),A7(0.035),A7(0.036),A7(0.037),A70(0.038),A8(0.039),A8(0.04),A8(0.041),A9(0.042)

A6 ->

A0(0.003),A0(0.006),A0(0.009),A0(0.011),A0(0.014),A0(0.017),A0(0.02),A0(0.023),A0(0.026),A10(0.028),A11(0.031),A14(0.034),A14(0.037),A14(0.04),A15(0.043),A16(0.046),A19(0.048),A20(0.051),A21(0.054),A23(0.057),A23(0.06),A7(0.063),A72(0.066),A8(0.068),A9(0.071),A9(0.074)

A70 -> A12(1.0)

A30 -> A0(0.1),A15(0.2),A26(0.3),A9(0.4)

A10 ->

A0(0.001),A0(0.001),A0(0.002),A0(0.002),A0(0.003),A0(0.004),A0(0.004),A0(0.005),A0(0.005),A10(0.006),A10(0.007),A10(0.007),A10(0.008),A10(0.008),A10(0.009),A10(0.01),A10(0.01),A11(0.011),A11(0.011),A11(0.012),A11(0.013),A11(0.013),A12(0.014),A12(0.015),A12(0.015),A13(0.016),A13(0.016),A13(0.017),A13(0.018),A14(0.018),A14(0.019),A16(0.019),A16(0.02),A18(0.021),A18(0.021),A18(0.022),A20(0.022),A21(0.023),A21(0.024),A22(0.024),A24(0.025),A25(0.025),A29(0.026),A6(0.027),A6(0.027),A6(0.028),A60(0.028),A7(0.029),A7(0.03),A7(0.03),A7(0.031),A8(0.031),A9(0.032),A9(0.033),A9(0.033),A9(0.034),A91(0.034)

A53 -> A13(1.0)

A60 -> A13(1.0)

A23 ->

A0(0.018),A0(0.036),A0(0.055),A10(0.073),A18(0.091),A19(0.109),A19(0.127),A21(0.145),A37(0.164),A8(0.182)

A14 ->

A0(0.002),A0(0.005),A10(0.007),A10(0.009),A11(0.011),A13(0.014),A13(0.016),A13(0.018),A13(0.021),A13(0.023),A13(0.025),A13(0.028),A14(0.03),A14(0.032),A14(0.034),A15(0.037),A15(0.039),A16(0.041),A16(0.044),A17(0.046),A17(0.048),A19(0.051),A20(0.053),A27(0.055),A29(0.057),A6(0.06),A7(0.062),A9(0.064),A9(0.067)

A9 ->

A0(0.001),A0(0.002),A0(0.004),A0(0.005),A0(0.006),A0(0.007),A0(0.009),A0(0.01),A10(0.011),A10(0.012),A11(0.013),A11(0.015),A12(0.016),A13(0.017),A13(0.018),A13(0.02),A13(0.021),A13(0.022),A15(0.023),A15(0.024),A16(0.026),A16(0.027),A16(0.028),A17(0.029),A17(0.03),A18(0.032),A19(0.033),A20(0.034),A21(0.035),A21(0.037),A32(0.038),A33(0.039),A39(0.04),A5(0.041),A57(0.043),A6(0.044),A8(0.045),A8(0.046),A8(0.048),A9(0.049)

A18 ->

A0(0.008),A0(0.017),A0(0.025),A0(0.033),A11(0.042),A14(0.05),A16(0.058),A17(0.067),A18(0.075),A20(0.083),A21(0.092),A27(0.1),A44(0.108),A7(0.117),A7(0.125)

A20 ->

A0(0.015),A11(0.03),A14(0.045),A14(0.061),A15(0.076),A16(0.091),A17(0.106),A18(0.121),A21(0.136),A23(0.152),A3(0.167)

A72 -> A14(1.0)

A27 -> A10(0.067),A11(0.133),A11(0.2),A16(0.267),A22(0.333)

A45 -> A24(0.333),A7(0.667)

A21 ->

A0(0.006),A0(0.012),A10(0.018),A12(0.023),A13(0.029),A13(0.035),A14(0.041),A14(0.047),A15(0.053),A19(0.058),A19(0.064),A22(0.07),A25(0.076),A28(0.082),A29(0.088),A32(0.094),A8(0.099),A8(0.105)

A57 -> A17(1.0)
A25 -> A11(0.036),A16(0.071),A16(0.107),A17(0.143),A25(0.179),A26(0.214),A8(0.25)
A91 -> A17(1.0)
A44 -> A17(1.0)
A29 -> A18(0.048),A19(0.095),A21(0.143),A27(0.19),A9(0.238),A9(0.286)
A22 -> A0(0.028),A12(0.056),A15(0.083),A21(0.111),A24(0.139),A30(0.167),A30(0.194),A8(0.222)
A24 -> A0(0.036),A15(0.071),A16(0.107),A17(0.143),A23(0.179),A26(0.214),A32(0.25)
A19 ->
A0(0.005),A10(0.011),A12(0.016),A12(0.021),A13(0.026),A18(0.032),A19(0.037),A20(0.042),A21(0.047),A21
(0.053),A23(0.058),A23(0.063),A25(0.068),A26(0.074),A28(0.079),A33(0.084),A39(0.089),A7(0.095),A8(0.1)
A28 -> A13(0.067),A19(0.133),A21(0.2),A28(0.267),A29(0.333)
A34 -> A22(1.0)
A37 -> A15(0.333),A33(0.667)
A32 -> A16(0.167),A22(0.333),A37(0.5)
A33 -> A20(0.167),A27(0.333),A30(0.5)
A39 -> A11(0.333),A45(0.667)
A26 -> A0(0.1),A25(0.2),A28(0.3),A68(0.4)

Figure 4: Fuzzification of Statistical data on fuel bookings in online shopping

Figure 5: Prediction of index and Quantity on fuel bookings in online shopping

Figure 6: Comparison of Forecasted price and Original Price of Statistical data on fuel bookings in online shopping

Conclusion:

Based on the results and discussion of the conclusions obtained from this study are the application of the FTS method to forecasting inflation in the Statistical data on fuel bookings in online shopping data pattern that is close to the actual data pattern. The FTS method has a better accuracy rate.

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